

Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Relation to Teachers' Performance

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Abstract:

This study examined the instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in relation to teachers' performance in Bindoy, Negros Oriental. A total of 176 public elementary teachers participated, classified by age, highest educational attainment, and length of service. Using a descriptive research design, data were collected via a self-made questionnaire and analyzed with descriptive, comparative, and relational methods. Statistical tools included frequency, percentage, mean, Mann-Whitney U test, and Spearman rho. Findings revealed that most respondents were younger (41 years old), had higher educational attainment, and a significant proportion had over 12 years of service. Instructional leadership skills in areas such as assessment of learning, instructional improvement, curriculum enhancement, and supervision were rated high. When grouped by age, highest educational attainment and length of service, school heads' leadership skills remained consistently high across these domains. No significant differences were found in instructional leadership skills regarding assessment of learning based on the aforementioned variables. However, significant differences emerged in instructional improvement, curriculum enhancement, and supervision when grouped by age and length of service but not by highest educational attainment. Teachers' performance showed no significant differences when analyzed by these factors. Additionally, no significant relationship existed between school heads' instructional leadership skills and teachers' performance.

Keywords: Instructional leadership skills, public elementary school heads, teachers' performance

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The effectiveness of schools largely depends on the instructional leadership skills of school heads, which inspire both teachers and students to reach their full potential as productive citizens (Republic Act 9155). Leadership, a crucial aspect for organizations globally, has gained increasing attention for its significant role in organizational success (Suraya, 2015). School leaders are expected to embody strong managerial qualities and possess specialized skills that enable them to manage tasks effectively and efficiently, ensuring success in their roles (Tiauzon, 2023). In the Philippines, instructional leadership practices include assessing learning, implementing instructional improvement programs, enhancing the curriculum, and overseeing supervision, all of which contribute to creating optimal teaching and learning environments (Ahmed, 2016).

Teachers' performance is a key determinant of school effectiveness and learning outcomes. Satisfied teachers tend to exhibit higher productivity and performance (Miñon, 2017). Thus, a harmonious relationship between school heads and teachers is crucial. In Bindoy, some teachers expressed dissatisfaction with their school heads' instructional leadership skills, occasionally leading to misunderstandings and formal complaints to the superintendent regarding perceived incompetence.

As a school head, the researcher was inspired to investigate the instructional leadership skills of school heads in relation to teachers' performance in Bindoy's public elementary schools. This study aims to provide valuable insights for enhancing leadership practices and improving teacher performance, ultimately supporting the goal of delivering quality basic education.

Current State of Knowledge

Bel (2018) examined the connection between administrators' instructional leadership styles and the school climate in the schools of Mati City, North District. The findings indicated that public administrators exhibited a high level of leadership, often demonstrating autocratic, democratic, managerial, and collaborative styles. The school climate was also rated as high, characterized by safety and learning, strong interpersonal relationships, and a conducive institutional environment. The study revealed a significant correlation between leadership style and school climate, emphasizing that effective leadership positively impacts the school climate.

Similarly, Varona (2017) investigated the leadership skills and attitudes of school heads as factors influencing school-community partnerships. The results highlighted that school heads possess strong leadership skills and exhibit highly positive attitudes toward fostering partnerships with the community. Additionally, a high degree of collaboration between schools and the community in various events was observed. The study further established a significant, direct, and moderate relationship between the leadership skills and attitudes of school heads and the extent of school-community collaboration.

In today's competitive environment, the vital role of teachers in shaping the youth of a nation often goes unrecognized. Teachers' performance, both within and beyond the classroom, plays a critical role in fostering students' personal and academic development. As role models, mentors, and nurturers, teachers set the tone for their classrooms, create supportive learning environments, and remain vigilant for signs of student distress. The success or failure of educational activities largely hinges on teacher performance. High performance is not only crucial for individual educators but also for the organizations they serve, enabling them to achieve their goals, deliver specialized services, and maintain a competitive edge. Job performance, generally defined as the act of completing assigned tasks, involves both behavioral and outcome-oriented aspects (Wula et al., 2020).

Hasbay and Altindag (2018) examined the factors affecting teachers' performance in secondary education, identifying wages, the working environment, and management as key variables. The study found that management practices had the most significant impact on teacher performance, followed by the working environment, while wages had a relatively minor direct influence. The results underscored the importance of creating a supportive administrative culture, ensuring effective communication, and offering career development opportunities for teachers. Additionally, the study suggested that teacher performance is enhanced in work environments where educators feel comfortable and are not subjected to excessive pressure. As Gernalin (2023) emphasizes, teachers go beyond their required working hours, performing their duties with passion and dedication to fulfill their responsibilities in fostering lifelong learners.

Similarly, Roberto and Madrigal (2019) assessed primary education teachers' competency levels based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and their performance using school-based evaluations. The results showed that teachers were rated as proficient and satisfactory in both teaching standards and performance, as evaluated by their principals and self-assessments. Variables such as sex, educational attainment, marital status, and employment status showed no significant differences in performance. However, the study found a meaningful relationship between teachers' level of competence and their overall performance, reinforcing the importance of maintaining high teaching standards for effective educational outcomes.

Moreover, Mensah and Yiadom (2019) conducted a study to assess instructional supervision practices in the Efutu Circuit of the Cape Coast Metropolis. The study revealed that instructional supervisors primarily conduct impromptu visits and class observations only when necessary. However, the use of lesson monitoring tools and syllabus coverage tools showed that clinical supervision, which could support teachers, is minimally practiced. Additionally, democratic collaboration to address instructional challenges and regular monitoring of instruction were lacking. The study found that teachers held varying and often negative attitudes toward instructional supervision. They noted that the current management approach tends to focus on identifying errors rather than fostering a collaborative environment. Teachers perceived the administration as more authoritative than democratic, with supervision functioning as an inspection rather than a cooperative process. Furthermore, they cited the time-consuming nature of the current management practices and a lack of sufficient support for improving teaching. Based on these findings, the study recommended that head teachers prioritize regular classroom observations, conduct them as needed, and enhance clinical supervision practices. As Sedigo (2024) emphasizes, school leaders should delegate authority and assign management roles within the school to strengthen leadership effectiveness.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The theories used in this study are the Instructional Leadership Theory by Goddard and Miller (2010) and the Job Performance Theory of J. P. Campbell (1990).

Instructional leadership theory highlights the essential role of educational leadership in enhancing teaching and learning by focusing on core school responsibilities, such as defining the mission and managing the learning environment. This theory emphasizes that leadership training equips principals with the knowledge and skills needed to identify high-quality instruction. It also enables them to support teachers through professional development,

ongoing encouragement, and regular monitoring, ultimately leading to improved classroom practices and higher student achievement. Consequently, instructional leadership serves as a foundational model for this study, given its focus on assessing the instructional leadership capabilities of school heads. Its emphasis on mentoring, modeling, and monitoring underscores its potential to drive school improvement and serve as a benchmark for school leaders.

Further supporting the relevance of this theory, Bellibas and Liu (2016) argue that fostering a positive learning climate is a key element of successful instructional leadership. A principal's behavior significantly influences the school climate, which, in turn, affects the motivation and collective efforts of teachers and staff toward shared goals. The principal's role in creating a supportive and conducive environment is vital for implementing effective instructional practices. Similarly, Goddard and Miller's (2010) perspective reinforces the importance of instructional leadership, highlighting the principal's responsibility in shaping an environment that prioritizes quality education. These insights affirm the applicability of instructional leadership theory to the present study, as it examines the school heads' role in promoting effective teaching and overall school performance.

Another theory of this study is anchored on the Job Performance Theory developed by J. P. Campbell in 1990. According to this theory, performance is the behavior or employee's actions that affect the goals and objectives of the organization. This behavior can be either positive or negative and can be either provided as part of the work or outside the scope of the duties set forth. Campbell (1990) defines performance as behavior, which is something done by an employee. This concept differentiates performance from outcomes. Outcomes result partially from an individual's performance, but they are also the result of other influences. In short, more factors determine outcomes than just an employee's behavior and actions. According to Campbell, however, performance needs to be under the individual's control, regardless of whether the performance of interest is mental or behavioral. Job Performance Theory can be liked in the present study for its deals with performance. With the essence of this theory, the researcher finds it complete with supporting and justifying the contents of the present study on the level of instructional leadership skills and teachers' performance. The researcher further believes that these factors have a great significant effect on the teachers' performance of public elementary schools in the municipality of Bindoy.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in relation to teachers' performance in the municipality of Bindoy, Negros Oriental: Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: 1) the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads as assessed by their teachers according to the area of assessment of learning, instructional improvement, curriculum enhancement and instructional supervision; 2) the level of teachers' performance when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 3) the significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads as assessed by their teachers when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the significant difference in the level of teachers' performance of public elementary school heads as assessed by their teachers when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 5) the significant relationship between public elementary school heads' level instructional leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design in determining the instructional leadership skills of schools heads and their relation to teachers' performance in the municipality of Bindoy, Negros Oriental. It is the nature of this study to determine the conditions of things in their present state. It delves into the relationships and comparisons among variables considered in this study and the influence of one variable on another. According to Nachimas and De Ward (2015), descriptive research is fact-finding with adequate interpretation. It is something more and beyond just data-gathering; the latter is not reflective thinking nor research. It describes and interprets what it is. It is concerned with conditions of relationships that exist; practices and beliefs, processes that are going on, effects that are being felt, or trends that are developing. Since the study is to determine the instructional leadership skills of school heads and it's influenced on teachers' performance, the descriptive research design is most appropriate for this study.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were public elementary school teachers in the municipality of Binoy. Since there are many teachers, the researcher used Cochran's Formula in determining the sample size. Since there are two districts,

the researcher used the stratified random sampling of the teacher-respondents. Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling technique that selects sub-samples proportionate in size to the significant characteristics of the total population (Faltado et al., 2016). Different strata in the population are defined, and each member of the stratum is listed, then simple random sampling is applied to each stratum

Instruments

This study utilized the researcher-made questionnaire and teachers' performance as secondary data. The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.92-excellent) and reliability (0.865-good). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The researcher-made questionnaire has two parts. The first part comprises the personal profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service. The second part of the questionnaire answers the instructional leadership skills. Instructional leadership is under domain 2 of the Training and Development Needs Assessment for School Heads (TDNASH). It will focus on the following areas: assessment for learning, instructional improvement, curriculum enhancement, and instructional supervision. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert's scale, which contains the following scores: 5 – Always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – Rarely, and 1 – Almost Never.

On the other hand, the secondary data for teachers' performance was requested upon the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Negros Oriental.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission through written communication from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education of the Division of Negros Oriental, requesting her to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires to the target respondents and to have full access to the teachers' performance. After granting permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to each respondent. The purpose of the study was adequately explained to respondents by the researcher. Likewise, consent to every respondent was also considered. In distributing the questionnaires, the researcher similarly used online platforms such as Google forms, messenger, Gmail, and other forms of electronic communications to limit face-to-face contact with the respondents. The data was tallied and tabulated with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No.1 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of instructional leadership skills as assessed by their teachers in the areas of assessment of learning, instructional improvement, and instructional supervision.

Objective No.2 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of teachers' performance.

Objective No. 3 used a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether a significant difference existed in the level of instructional leadership skills as assessed by their teachers when they are grouped and compared according to variables mentioned above.

Objective No. 4 used a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of teachers' performance when grouped and compared according to variables.

Objective No. 5 used a relational analytical scheme and Spearman *rho* to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the level of instructional leadership skills of schools heads and teachers' performance.

Ethical Consideration

In ensuring the validity and reliability of the data, analysis, and findings, several critical issues were addressed. Ethical considerations were strictly adhered to throughout the study. The researcher clearly and thoroughly explained the purpose of the study to the respondents and disclosed the name of the school and participants involved, fulfilling the ethical obligation to obtain informed consent. All data collected—whether through the survey responses or secondary sources—were exclusively used for the purposes of this research. The researcher maintained objectivity by refraining from inserting personal opinions or judgments into the analysis. Furthermore, all data and information gathered were treated with strict confidentiality to protect the privacy and integrity of the respondents and the institution.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the area Assessment of Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I observed that our school heads.		
1. ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance.	4.18	High Level
2. manage the processes and procedures in monitoring student achievement	4.10	High Level
3. assess the effectiveness of curricular/co-curricular programs and instructional strategies	4.11	High Level
4. create and manage a school process to ensure student progress is conveyed to students and parents/guardians regularly.	4.09	High Level
5. utilize assessment results to improve learning	4.11	High Level
6. share expertise with other school heads in the development of programs to address assessment needs	4.13	High Level
7. prioritize school programs to address pupils' learning needs	4.07	High Level
8. conduct action research on pupils performance	2.94	Moderate Level
9. develop intervention programs such as remedial and reading programs	4.12	High Level
10. supervise assessment techniques	4.14	High Level
Over-all Mean	3.88	High Level

As revealed, respondents assessed item No. 1 as the highest mean score of 4.35, which states "ensure utilization of a range of assessment processes to assess student performance" interpreted as "high level." In contrast, item No. 8 has the lowest mean score of 2.94, which states "conduct action research on pupil's performance" interpreted as "moderate level." The overall mean was 3.88, interpreted as "high level."

This implies that school heads ensure that a range of assessment process is being utilized by teachers. School heads must also take the lead in the conduct of action research to determine the factors that influence low pupils' performance and develop programs to address pupils' learning needs. They must initiate actions to create possibilities for the future by utilizing assessment results.

According to Lanuza (2015), teachers and school heads consider teaching and assessing learning as essential strategies to effect improvement. They anticipate obstacles to overcome them and hope for success rather than failure; hence, they all exhibited personal fulfillment in general. In addition, according to Umar (2018), assessment for learning is based on providing instant and specific feedback after each learning step to avoid unnecessary delay in correcting students' errors. For such evaluation to realize its maximum benefit, it is suggested that assessment should not be a once-and-done activity. Instead, it must be a continuous act, which guides the teaching-learning process by providing timely feedback. It is widely acknowledged that feedback is enhanced if and only if it is immediate and clearly articulated to guide the learning process and rectify possible shortcomings. Thus, teachers are encouraged to conduct action research on students' learning to come up with immediate solutions.

Table 2

Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the area Instructional Improvement

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I observed that our school heads.		
1. implement the prescribed K to 12 curriculum	4.97	Very High Level
2. assist in implementing an existing, coherent, and responsive school-wide curriculum	4.34	High Level
3. address deficiencies and sustain the success of current programs in collaboration with teachers and learners	4.34	High Level
4. develop a culture of functional literacy	4.20	High Level
5. develop/adapt a research-based school program	3.29	Moderate Level
6. conduct meetings with subject area leaders to align content with standards	4.51	Very High Level
7. identify gaps and successes in the school instructional program	4.30	High Level
8. facilitate the use of effective teaching-learning materials to address deficiencies	4.33	High Level
9. develop programs to ensure effective learning happens.	4.32	High Level
10. provide expertise in assessing their curriculum programs	4.31	High Level

Over-all Mean **4.25 High Level**

As revealed in Table 2, respondents assessed item No. 1 as the highest mean score of 4.97, which states "implement the prescribed K to 12 curricula" interpreted as "very high level" while item No. 5 as the lowest mean score of 3.29 which states "develop/adopt a research-based school program" interpreted as "moderate level." The overall mean was 4.25, interpreted as "high level."

The facts above imply that there was a very high level in the implementation of the K to 12 curricula. It is understandable since they are the ones who take the lead in developing and implementing the program. On the other hand, school heads should also develop a school-based research program to coordinate with their teachers to develop a better strategy for improvement. Benchmark with other school heads and share ideas to generate better plans to address the deficiencies of the curriculum.

According to Daing (2015), instructional leadership should emphasize the teaching and learning aspects of school leadership and highlight organizational management for instructional improvement. Organizational management for instructional improvement means staffing a school with high-quality teachers and providing them with the appropriate supports and resources to be successful in the classroom.

Table 3
Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the area Curriculum Enhancement

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I observed that our school head.		
1. manage the introduction of curriculum initiatives in line with DepEd policies (e.g., BEC, Madrasah)	4.59	Very High Level
2. manage curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology	4.65	Very High Level
3. enrich curricular offerings based on local needs	4.58	Very High Level
4. work with teachers in curriculum review	4.61	Very High Level
5. organize teams to champion instructional innovation programs toward curricular responsiveness	4.69	Very High Level
6. identify instructional standards based on the curriculum and teacher's guide	4.53	Very High Level
7. align curriculum to learning standards	4.47	High Level
8. involve teachers in reinforcing /enriching curricular offerings	4.55	Very High Level
9. formulate intervention programs/ innovations for learners development	3.68	High Level
10. use technology and multiple sources of instructional materials to improve classroom instruction.	4.66	Very High Level
Over-all Mean	4.33	High Level

As shown in Table 3, respondents assessed item No. 5 as the highest mean score of 4.69, which states "organize teams to champion instructional innovation programs toward curricular responsiveness" interpreted as "very high level." While item No. 9 is the lowest mean score of 3.68, it states "formulate intervention programs/ innovations for learners' development" interpreted as "high level." The overall mean was 4.33, interpreted as "high level."

The data as mentioned above implies that school heads are exercising their best to ensure that the curriculum is in line with DepEd policies, ensuring alignment of curriculum standards and managing curriculum innovations using technology. But on the other side, school heads must also lead in formulating interventions/ innovations for learners' development. Work with teachers to craft intervention plans to meet the instructional needs of the learners.

It is the responsibility of the school heads to provide instructional leadership, which entails ensuring high-quality teaching and learning by enhancing instructional programs and ensuring effective use of instructional time to foster the attainment of educational goals and objectives. Similarly, Onuma (2016) asserted that the school has the primary functions of exhibiting effective instructional leadership practices to improve diversified curriculum and quality of the instructional program for effective attainment of set school goals.

Table 4
Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the area Instructional Supervision

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a school head, to what level do I.		
1. conduct Instructional Supervision using an appropriate strategy	4.35	High Level
2. prepare and implement an instructional supervisory plan	4.32	High Level

3. provide expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers	4.39	High Level
4. provide in a collegial manner timely, accurate, and specific feedback to teachers regarding their performance	4.45	High Level
5. evaluate lesson plans as well as classroom and learning management	4.26	High Level
6. check lesson plans/logs as to the alignment from objective down to assessment	4.16	High Level
7. supervise classroom instruction according to Division guidelines	4.11	High Level
8. conduct a post-conference after the actual observation	4.13	High Level
9. encourage the professional growth of individuals based on observed data	4.29	High Level
10. provide feedback during conferences, informal visits, and meetings with teachers	4.13	High Level
Over-all Mean	4.18	High Level

As manifested in table 4, respondents assessed item No. 4 as the highest mean score of 4.45, which states "provide in a collegiate manner timely, accurate and specific feedback to teachers regarding their performance" interpreted as "high level" while item No. 7 as the lowest mean score of 4.11 which states "supervise classroom instruction according to Division guidelines" interpreted as "high level." The overall mean was 4.18, interpreted as "high level."

This implies that school heads are exhibiting their best in instructional supervision. They also provide accurate and specific feedback to teachers concerning their performance. But most of the teachers urge that the school head' must adhere to division guidelines on classroom supervision, conduct post-conference after the observation, provide feedback to teachers, and encourage the professional growth of their teachers to improve instructional competence in classrooms.

Clark (2015) sees supervision as a task of improving instruction through regular monitoring and in-service education of teachers. He also highlighted that instructional supervision is the act of checking, watching, and observing the activities of teachers, which is geared toward coaching and mentoring them and providing professional guidance, direction, leadership, and assistance for professional development to improve the quality of instructional delivery.

Table 5
Teachers' Performance According to the Variables, Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.44	Very Satisfactory
	Older	4.44	Very Satisfactory
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	4.44	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.44	Very Satisfactory
Length of Service	Lower	4.44	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.44	Very Satisfactory

As revealed in table 5, teachers when grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, and length of service performed a very satisfactory level. This shows that teachers are doing their best in performing their duties as teachers. Despite of the difficulties they encountered and despite the pandemic, their desire to teach will always continue. They always act as role models and advocate in upholding the dignity of the teaching profession, Likewise, the welfare of every learner must be present at all times. In order for teachers to maintain a high level of professional performance for these conditions, they must assume personal responsibility for their own performance, growth, and development (Anderson, 2015).

Table 6
Difference in the Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the Area Assessment of Learning According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	92	87.28	3751.50	0.737		Not Significant
	Older	84	89.84				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	64	86.53	3458.00	0.696	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	112	89.63				
Length of Service	Lower	86	89.06	3821.50	0.885		Not Significant
	Higher	90	87.96				

As depicted in the table, for variable age, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3751.5 with a p -value of 0.737, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of assessment of learning as assessed by teachers according to age was accepted.

Meanwhile, for variable highest educational attainment, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3458.0 with a p -value of 0.696, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of assessment of learning as assessed by teachers according to highest educational attainment was accepted.

Further, for variable length of service, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3821.5 with a p -value of 0.885, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of assessment of learning as assessed by teachers according to length of service was accepted.

This would mean that the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of assessment of learning as assessed by teachers when they are grouped and compared according to age, educational attainment, and length of service do not vary.

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the Area Instructional Improvement According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U-test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	92	76.02	2715.500	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Older	84	102.17				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	64	84.27	3313.00	0.400	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	112	90.92				
Length of Service	Lower	86	65.15	1862.00	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	90	110.81				

As divulged in the table, for variable age, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 2715.5 with a p -value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of instructional improvement as assessed by teachers according to age was rejected.

Whereas for variable highest educational attainment, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3313.0 with a p -value of 0.400, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of instructional improvement as assessed by teachers according to highest educational attainment was accepted.

Further, for variable length of service, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 1862.0 with a p -value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of instructional improvement as assessed by teachers according to length of service was rejected.

This would mean that the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in instructional improvement as assessed by teachers when they are grouped and compared according to age and length of service differs while grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment do not differs. This is because older and longer in service teachers had already experienced various challenges on instructional programs so they can easily adapt to the new teaching methods such as modular and online distance learning.

Table 8

Difference in the Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the Area Curriculum Enhancement According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	92	75.96	2710.00	0.001	0.05	Significant

Highest Educational Attainment	Older	84	102.24	3513.00	0.825	Not Significant
	Lower	64	87.39			
Length of Service	Higher	112	89.13	2807.00	0.001	Significant
	Lower	86	76.14			
	Higher	90	100.31			

As shown in the table, for variable age, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 2710.0 with a p -value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of curriculum enhancement as assessed by teachers according to age was rejected.

For variable highest educational attainment, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3513.0 with a p -value of 0.825, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant". Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of curriculum enhancement as assessed by teachers according to highest educational attainment was accepted.

Further, for variable length of service, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 2807.0 with a p -value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of curriculum enhancement as assessed by teachers according to the length of service was rejected.

This would mean that the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in curriculum enhancement as assessed by teachers when they are grouped and compared according to age and length of service varies while grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment do not vary. This is because older and longer in-service teachers are knowledgeable with the curriculum and involve themselves in enriching curricular offerings with the supervision of the school heads. Onuma (2016) asserted that the school heads have the primary functions of exhibiting effective instructional leadership practices to improve diversified curriculum and quality of the instructional program for effective attainment of set school goals.

Table 9

The difference in the Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads as assessed by their teachers in the Area Instructional Supervision According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	92	71.54	2304.00	0.000		Significant
	Older	84	107.07				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	64	93.44	3268.00	0.328	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	112	85.68				
Length of Service	Lower	86	69.77	2259.00	0.000		Significant
	Higher	90	106.40				

As presented in the table, for variable age, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 2304.0 with a p -value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of instructional as assessed by teachers according to age was rejected.

For variable highest educational attainment, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 3268.0 with a p -value of 0.328, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of instructional supervision as assessed by teachers according to highest educational attainment was accepted.

Further, for a variable length of service, the computed Mann Whitney U-test was 2259.0 with a p -value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the area of supervision as assessed by teachers according to the length of service was rejected.

This implies that the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads in instructional supervision as assessed by teachers when grouped and compared according to age and length of service differs while grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment do not differ. This is because older and longer in-service teachers had already spent a number of years in service. They had already experienced different supervisory styles by their previous and present school heads.

Table 10
The difference in the Level of Teachers' Performance According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	92	86.32	3663.00	0.496		Not Significant
	Older	84	90.89				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	64	88.80	3565.00	0.947	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	112	88.33				
Length of Service	Lower	86	85.46	3608.50	0.376		Not Significant
	Higher	90	91.41				

As presented in the table, the computed Mann Whitney U test for variable age was 3663.0, for highest educational attainment was 3565.0 and for the length of service was 3608.5, while the *p*-values were 0.496, 0.947, and 0.376, respectively; the computed *p*-values were all greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of teachers' performance when they are grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment and length of service" was accepted.

This implies that the level of teachers' performance does not vary; they are grouped and compared according to, highest educational attainment and length of service. Teacher performance in the classroom plays a crucial role in students' learning process. It is the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Teachers weave a combination of their knowledge, skills, and abilities into specific performance competencies that become drivers of student learning and achievement. Usop (2015) noted that educators who are contented with their job maintain a high level of performance. Teachers who are satisfied with their work are also productive workers (Mifion, 2017).

Table 11
Relationship Between the Level of Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads and the Level of Teachers' Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Instructional Leadership Teachers' Performance	0.099	0.191	0.05	Not Significant

As presented in the table, the computed *r_s* was 0.099 with a *p*-value of 0.191, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant relationship existed between the level of instructional leadership skills of public elementary school heads and teachers' performance" was accepted.

This implies that public elementary school heads' level of instructional leadership skills was not a contributing factor in improving teachers' performance.

These findings were supported by the study of Chiedozi and Victor (2017). Their study revealed that there is no significant relationship in the mean rating of principals and teachers on principals' application of instructional supervision practices for secondary school effectiveness in secondary schools in Oyo State.

The findings of Daing's (2015) study revealed a significant relationship between the instructional leadership skills of the schools' heads and the teachers' rating based on a results-based performance management system.

The researcher recommends that the school heads seriously consider all the indicators of the four areas of instructional leadership skills. Furthermore, the school heads and other school managers shall create new programs or strengthen existing leadership training and programs to sustain the school's level of instructional leadership skills and teachers' performance. The gathered data from this study can also be used as resource material for an added information and enhancement.

Conclusions:

In conclusions, the study revealed that public elementary school heads demonstrated high levels of instructional leadership skills across various domains, including assessing learning, implementing instructional improvement programs, curriculum enhancement, and instructional supervision. However, areas for improvement were identified, such as conducting action research on pupils' performance, adopting research-based school programs, and strictly adhering to Division guidelines in classroom supervision. Advanced training for school heads in formulating intervention programs was also recommended. Teachers performed at a very satisfactory level regardless of their age, highest educational attainment, or length of service, though their perceptions of school heads' instructional leadership skills varied based on age and experience. Notably, the instructional leadership skills of school heads did not significantly impact teachers' performance ratings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is recommended that the division training and development team conduct quarterly needs-based seminars and action research activities to enhance the research knowledge and skills of school heads and teachers. School heads should strengthen their instructional leadership by focusing on assessment, instructional improvement, curriculum enhancement, and supervision while providing technical and instructional support to teachers. To address gaps in research-based program implementation, supervisors and school heads should organize training and technical assistance to help teachers develop school-based research and intervention plans, with teams formed to identify and address deficiencies. Regular assessment and training of school heads by district supervisors are also necessary for optimal performance. For curriculum enhancement, school heads should lead the development of instructional innovations and intervention programs in collaboration with teams, benchmark best practices, and seek coaching from high-performing peers, scheduling these activities during the 1st and 3rd quarters of the school year. District supervisors must monitor school heads' practices and provide technical assistance to ensure effective instructional supervision, while school heads should provide timely professional guidance to teachers. Teachers are encouraged to foster strong collaboration with school heads, support school programs, and maintain a shared vision to promote effective teaching and a positive learning environment. Lastly, a similar study is recommended to explore variables like time management, school assignment distance, and stress management for deeper insights into instructional leadership.

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